

The Technician Commitment: Championing technical skills, roles and careers

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Question	Answer
<p>Is 'technician' the same as 'professional' (vs academic)?</p>	<p>Often in the UK technicians are similarly within the 'Professional Services' job family and whilst technical roles are fundamentally different to other professional services both are required. Further information, aka a fuller answer, and background can be seen at the blog by Kelly Vere highlighted in the presentation.</p> <p>https://wonkhe.com/blogs/technical-professionals-can-offer-more-than-support/</p>
<p>Do you have recommended practices for how academics should acknowledge technicians in the Acknowledgments sections of journal articles (in cases where they don't qualify for authorship), including metadata recommendations? I'm working on this and would love to chat with someone about it.</p>	<p>Yes! Many of our organisation have a Fair Attribution Policy (or similar) to ensure technicians are properly recognised for their contribution to all publications, either as authors or in acknowledgements etc Please do reach out to discuss but a couple of random examples are below; there are many more that may better suit your particular organisation.</p> <p>https://www.nottingham.ac.uk/technicians/fair-attribution.aspx https://www.durham.ac.uk/about-us/technician-commitment/about-us/news/fair-attribution-policy/ https://researchculture.leeds.ac.uk/technician-commitment/678-2/ https://warwick.ac.uk/research/technicians/fairattribution/</p>
<p>So by being a signatory an organisation is making a decision on behalf of staff to choose the pathway as technician (and not as a professional. I suppose both are not synonyms). Or Staff choose if they pursue this pathway or not?</p>	<p>By becoming a signatory the organisation is pledging to support its technical staff and work to increase their visibility and recognition as well as providing career development opportunities and safeguarding technical skills. Where</p>

	<p>organisations develop a career pathway for technicians, then often the choice as to whether to switch to that pathway is left down to the individual (see for example the RTP Pathway at the University of Liverpool, links below) but this would be a decision taken by the institution in consultation with technical staff.</p>
<p>Do you have a list for the contact person for the Technicians' Commitment at each university that has signed it? Hoping to find out who that is at the University of Sydney!</p>	<p>Yes. I cannot share this here for confidentiality of personal information reasons but if you contact me either directly or through tc@itss.org.uk I am sure we can make the contact</p>
<p>I am curious about the data technicians, how are those trained and what's their role?</p>	<p>Not entirely sure I understand this question but an increasingly important aspect of many technicians' role is data stewardship and, through the ITSS Learning and Development Academy, we are providing training on aspects around working with GitHub, Power BI and similar, alongside Careers in Research Software Engineering for example. We are also aware of a number of other organisations and individual institutions providing training in data stewardship and the like.</p>
<p>Where do librarians sit with respect to the technician commitment? Just library techs, but not librarians included?</p>	<p>As I mentioned in the Q&A session itself, we purposefully do not define a technician but ask Signatories and Supporters to do so as part of their initial self-assessment. I think the best way to answer this question though is to let Research Libraries UK do so, as they are the experts, and so please see link below. Having said that, we, as a Commitment we are very happy for librarians to be part of the community.</p> <p>https://www.rluk.ac.uk/rluk-technician-commitment/</p>
<p>Is there a piece of work - re: budget support - that is available for institutes that rely on grants etc where it can help elevate the funding for technicians?</p>	<p>Not quite sure what this question is driving at but one of the things we are keen to do is ensure all technicians within an organisation, be they 'grant funded' or 'core funded' are treated equitably. For example, the ten days CPD time for technicians that is becoming a norm applies irrespective of funding. We are an inclusive initiative.</p>

	<p>On funding of technicians then, for the UK we have published an explainer.</p> <p>https://itss.org.uk/wp-content/uploads/2024/12/Funding-Technical-Staff-In-Research.pdf</p>
<p>We have noticed there are excellent opportunities for recognition in the UK/US but limited in Aus - are there any external awards and scientific committees that Australians can apply for and should be championing?</p>	<p>I am not sufficiently knowledgeable of the Australian ecosystem to comment too much on this, apologies. I am aware that the Times Higher Education (who run the awards including Outstanding Technician of the Year here in the UK/Ireland) also run in Asia and MENA so maybe one to explore as a HE community? I am happy to discuss this directly in more detail if helpful.</p>
<p>Any comments on how this aligns with the idea of Staff scientists type roles?</p>	<p>The UKRI definition of a technician and list of job titles that I shared "Staff Scientist" is included. As mentioned earlier, inclusion is a fundamental principle of the Technician Commitment and so from our point of view a staff scientist role would be well aligned with the Technician Commitment and, although it is for autonomous institutions to define a technician then we would expect such a role to be included with the initiative.</p>
<p>How is the career pathways initiative impacted by using short-term roles and contracts for resourcing due to a reliance on "soft money" and external grants? - basically how do you get organisations to think long-term and invest in ongoing roles for technicians?</p>	<p>Precurity of contracts (repeated short-term contracts that are grant funding dependent) is a real challenge for the sector in the UK. Through our work, institutions are now beginning to understand their technical community, and the skills they have much better, and recognise the need to retain and refresh those skills. One of the major developments has been the appointment of Strategic Technical Leads within institutions that can both advocate for technicians and technical skills at senior executive level but can also have an institutional view of the current and future skills portfolio. Please see the Strategic Technical Leadership: Advocacy, Empowerment and Transformation report</p> <p>https://itss.org.uk/wp-content/uploads/2024/11/Strategic_Technical_Leadership_Report.pdf</p>
<p>How explicitly or implicitly do you include IT & software professionals as technicians in the</p>	<p>At the risk of repeating then it is up to individual institutions how they define a</p>

<p>TC? Are there challenges in making the tent bigger, because the concerns of the different technical career paths differ?</p>	<p>technician. We are, however, finding that over time as the Technician Commitment becomes embedded in institutions then IT and software professionals such as Research Software Engineers actively 'want' to engage: they are coming to institutional leads to understand more about the Technician Commitment! There are indeed challenges in making the tent bigger but as the Technician Commitment is a deceptively simple document based on a set of principles around supporting and developing all staff with a technical aspect to their role, these challenges can be, and have been, overcome.</p>
<p>Also how do you connect with more specialist organisations? Thinking like the Royal Society of Microscopy.</p>	<p>The Royal Microscopical Society, and indeed BioImaging UK are already formal supporters of the Technician Commitment (links below) as our aims and objectives around supporting people are so well aligned.</p> <p>As a more general response then we connect primarily through people – networking! Often simply reaching out through our existing networks is fruitful as many such organisations are really very keen to engage.</p> <p>https://www.rms.org.uk/community/technician-commitment.html</p>
<p>In Australia, who a tech is seems to fall into level of qualification. Tech roles often only require one to attend tafe or smaller uni course/apprenticeships, researchers have the longer 'higher' uni qualifications. then within an organisation seem to be adding a term such as admin techs (think IT), compared to motor techs, research techs and then the organisation focuses on how it supports what type of techs it has.</p>	<p>This is more of a comment than a question, but I would note that as part of our work on career pathways we recognised that we need to encourage many different entry routes to ensure we have a diverse workforce. We have worked hard through the ITSS on the sustainability pillar of the Technician Commitment encouraging young people into T Levels, apprenticeships, degree apprenticeships and the like to ensure we have a rich and diverse pipeline of technical talent. We also encourage institutions to have a broad definition of technician and to support all technical staff equally.</p>
<p>Should hybrid (professional/academic) 'third space' roles be tackled on a per uni</p>	<p>Being based in the UK then I cannot comment specifically on this but in the UK</p>

<p>Enterprise Bargaining Agreement (EBA) basis, or is this a wider National Tertiary Education Union (NTEU) issue?</p>	<p>we have nationally agreed pay scales within which 'spine points' correspond to pay. The grades that are allocated to each spine point, and the way in which staff move through these grades (role review, regrading, promotion) is defined institutionally.</p>
<p>What's the best way to get engagement and to identify what job positions are classified as technician?</p>	<p>The best way to get engagement is through talking to people – networking! Be that internal with technical colleagues from other departments or external through conferences, regional/national meetings and the like.</p> <p>Identification of job positions that are classified as technician is actually the most important first step for any institution: defining your community is critical to success. This task is often more challenging, and time consuming than one would think it would or indeed should be. We encourage institutions to work on this at the start (hence it is our first question in the self-assessment!) but also recognise that as the Technician Commitment develops and becomes embedded then the community will evolve and grow.</p>
<p>What are some steps a company can make to determine career/salary growth across industry? Seems a bit daunting and free-for-all</p>	<p>For clarity the Technician Commitment is for the Higher Education and Research (Institute) sector. We have had some discussions with a number of company representatives about what a Technician Commitment for the industrial/commercial sector could look like but that is not a step we have (yet!) taken.</p> <p>On the broader point around determining career growth for technicians when there is currently no defined career path then I would simply say start! For many years in the UK, the development of career pathways for technicians was on the 'too hard to do' pile for a number of good, and some bad, reasons, and to be honest it is not easy. However, a significant, and increasing number of institutions have done this proving it can be done, but you need to start!</p>

<p>How do you carve a path for career progression where there is no set path?</p>	<p>If the question is institutional, then I would respond as above – start the work! Also, use the resources available from here in the UK to help and support. The beacon activity work at Liverpool and Warwick (links below) are great places to start understanding.</p> <p>If the question was about an individual, then I would equally simply say take every opportunity you can! Be that in terms of training, working with others, supporting a different project or anything really! Keep enhancing your skill set and CV and be ready for the next career move before it becomes available – be prepared.</p> <p>As a slight aside then the Technician Commitment is launching a podcast in late February 2026 (see social media – LinkedIn – for details) and the first of these is with Jiteen Ahmed who is the Times Higher Education Awards Outstanding Technician of the Year award winner this year and he is talking about his career journey. Hopefully this is not a spoiler, but Jiteen started as an apprentice at Aston University directly after school and has recently been appointed as Head of Technical Services for the entire University clearly showing that you can carve a path for career progression where there is no set path! So, listen in and he will answer this much better than I can.</p> <p>https://www.liverpool.ac.uk/research/research-environment/enabling-environment/research-technical-pathway/ https://www.liverpool.ac.uk/media/livacuk/How_to_create_your_RTP_CAREER_PATHWAY.pdf https://warwick.ac.uk/research/technicians/technicalspecialistspromotionalframeworkpilott/ https://warwick.ac.uk/research/technicians/93663 - uow technician commitment brochure_web.pdf</p>
<p>How do we promote our value in the eyes of the organisation without destroying the work life balance we currently enjoy?</p>	<p>Visibility and recognition of the hugely valuable work technicians do is separate and distinct from workload. The HE sector</p>

	<p>in the UK has been through some very (financially) challenging times over the last number of years resulting in voluntary redundancies and in some cases compulsory redundancies and technical staff have not been immune to this. This reduction in FTE/headcount has had impact on workload and we recognise that, but it has also given us the opportunity to look at how we work to ensure that the technical sector in HE is fit for the future.</p> <p>Now is exactly the time at which we need to be clearly articulating the value of the work we do that underpins and delivers so much of the research, teaching and knowledge exchange that Universities do. To be fair, it is not easy but we must do it.</p>
<p>Why do academics or management treat Technical Officer as a Technician while they are highly skilled and experienced?</p>	<p>I would respectfully push back on the premise of this question. In my reading of this it is implicit in the question that being treated 'as a technician' is somehow devaluing. It is not. We should strive for a culture where being treated 'as a technician' is a compliment highlighting that all colleagues and stakeholders are aware of the critical expertise, enormous wealth of skills and incredibly valuable experience they hold. We are most definitely not, I repeat NOT, 'just a technician'!</p>